

Unequal Access to Clinical Exposure: A Policy Brief for Pre-Health Students in California

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Executive Summary

Clinical exposure, such as shadowing and observation, is a foundational element of obtaining an education centered around human health, yet access to shadowing opportunities in California is incredibly inconsistent. Many hospitals prohibit shadowing entirely or require liability processes that differ from location to location. As a result of this, access inherently depends on personal connections, competitive programs, or informal advocacy rather than merit or interest in health care.

This policy brief proposes a standardized, optional statewide clinical observation liability waiver for supervised pre-health students aged 18 and older. The goal within this is not to mandate shadowing, but to try and reduce the administrative inconsistency that disproportionately limits access for students who lack resources, such as but not limited to, low income and first generation students.

This is a low cost and low risk policy idea that supports equity in healthcare while still preserving the autonomy of the hospital.

The Problem

Pre health students are expected to gain clinical exposure to confirm their interest in medicine, dentistry, and other allied health professions. However, hospitals all across California apply uneven and often restrictive liability policies that make shadowing either difficult or impossible. Some healthcare institutions prohibit shadowing entirely. Other hospitals require specific waivers, an internal recommendation, or staff connections. These inconsistencies make barriers that fall mostly on students without direct access to medical professionals.

As a result of this, a lot of students are blocked from essential exposure before they can even determine if a healthcare career is the right career for them.

Evidence From Students and Institutions

Student Testimonies (Verbatim)

S1 A pre-med master's student described the current reality of trying to shadow:

"You need to get in there to really see what's going on [...] I've watched a lot but it's been with push and shove, asking for any and every opportunity to get in there and learn.

They further noted:

"I've shadowed officially at outpatient centers and those are diff[erent] compared to big chain hospitals [...] for example, Sharp out here in SD doesn't let people shadow."

S2 Another pre-health student emphasized the role of access to hospitals below:

“Unfortunately when you do not have staff support that have connections, etc. it is very difficult to get shadowing or clinic hours.”

They added:

“Majority of these internship programs are very competitive and scarce [...] only maybe up to 20 people are accepted.”

And finally concluded:

“I definitely feel like if I didn’t have these opportunities I would not have received the experience I have today.”

Institutional Feedback (Summarized)

A volunteer coordinator at a local, large California healthcare system explained that:

- Liability requirements for shadowing and volunteering vary by location
- There is not a standardized system wide approach
- The coordinator further stated, *“I don’t know how it would affect us positively or negatively, but if it helps everyone, it helps everyone.”*

All of this confirms that inconsistency is the main barrier, not a lack of interest.

Why This Matters for Health Equity

When access to clinical exposure depends on connections or acceptance into competitive programs, students from low income and first generation backgrounds are inherently excluded. Early clinical exposure helps students solidify their career decisions, helps prepare students for their intended healthcare professions, and supports a more diverse workforce of our future healthcare workers.

Policy Proposal: A Standardized Shadowing Liability Waiver

This brief proposed the creation of a standardized, optional, statewide clinical shadowing liability waiver with the following characteristics:

- Applies to supervised shadowing only
- Available for pre health students over the age of 18
- Optional implementation by hospitals and clinics
- Provides a legally consistent template, not a mandate
- Preserves hospital discretion over participation and capacity

The goal is to reduce administrative constraints, not to force institutions to allow students to shadow.

Considerations

This proposal requires no new funding, doesn’t mandate participation, and could be offered as a best practice framework. Hospitals would still have full control over whether and how they allow shadowing, while students benefit from clearer pathways to said shadowing.

Conclusion

Inconsistent liability policies create unnecessary barriers to clinical exposure for aspiring healthcare professionals. A standardized, optional shadowing waiver represents a very practical step toward equity in the pre health pipeline. By addressing this issue early in pathway, California can support students who want to pursue medicine, nursing, and similar professions, regardless of background or personal connections.